

PHYTOCHEMICAL INVESTIGATION AND PHARMACOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF SESBANIA SESBAN LEAF FOR ANTI-ULCER ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

The present study was undertaken to investigate the pharmacognostic characteristics, phytochemical profile, antioxidant potential, and anti-ulcer activity of Sesbania sesban leaf extracts. The plant material was collected, authenticated, and subjected to standard pharmacognostic and physicochemical evaluation, which confirmed its identity, purity, and quality. Successive solvent extraction revealed maximum extractive value in methanol (30%), followed by ethyl acetate (26%) and ethanol (18%), indicating the presence of predominantly polar phytoconstituents. Preliminary phytochemical screening demonstrated the presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds, alkaloids, glycosides, and steroids. Quantitative estimation showed higher total phenolic content (32.8%) and total flavonoid content (36.5%) in the ethanol extract compared to the ethyl acetate extract. The

antioxidant activity, evaluated using the DPPH assay, exhibited significant concentration-dependent free radical scavenging, with ethanol extract showing 92.68% inhibition at 125 µg/mL, comparable to standard antioxidants such as rutin, gallic acid, and ascorbic acid. Acute oral toxicity studies, conducted as per OECD, indicated that the extracts were safe up to 2000 mg/kg body weight. The anti-ulcer activity was evaluated using an ethanol-induced gastric ulcer model in experimental animals. Both ethyl acetate and ethanol extracts demonstrated significant gastroprotective effects in a dose-dependent manner. At 200 mg/kg, ethyl acetate and ethanol extracts showed 73.06% and 70.29% ulcer protection, respectively,

which were comparable to the standard drug ranitidine (79.44%). Additionally, both extracts significantly increased gastric pH and reduced total acidity. The findings suggest that *Sesbania sesban* possesses potent antioxidant and anti-ulcer activities, which may be attributed to its rich phenolic and flavonoid content. The study provides scientific validation for the traditional use of the plant and highlights its potential as a natural therapeutic agent for the management of gastric ulcers.

KEYWORD: *Sesbania sesban*, Anti-ulcer activity; Antioxidant activity, Ethanol-induced gastric ulcer, Ranitidine.

INTRODUCTION

An ulcer is defined as a pathological lesion characterized by a break in the continuity of epithelial tissue, occurring either externally on the skin or internally within body organs. It typically presents as an open sore that may extend into deeper tissues, often accompanied by inflammation, pain, and bleeding. Ulcers may also develop due to prolonged pressure on tissues, especially in individuals with limited mobility. Cutaneous ulcers generally appear as crater-like lesions with inflamed, swollen, and tender surrounding tissue.^[1]

Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) is one of the most common gastrointestinal disorders worldwide. It is characterized by the formation of lesions in the mucosal lining of the stomach or the proximal part of the small intestine (duodenum). The disease results from an imbalance between aggressive factors such as gastric acid, pepsin, alcohol consumption, smoking, stress, and certain medications, and defensive mechanisms including mucus secretion, bicarbonate production, prostaglandins, and mucosal blood flow. Although several pharmacological treatments, including proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), H₂-receptor antagonists, and antacids, are available, long-term use of these drugs is often associated with adverse effects such as drug interactions, tolerance, and recurrence. Therefore, there is growing interest in identifying safer and more effective anti-ulcer agents from natural sources.^[2]

Types of Ulcers

Ulcers are classified based on their anatomical location and underlying causes. The major types include genital ulcers, pressure ulcers, anal fissures, diabetic foot ulcers, corneal ulcers, ulcerative dermatitis, aphthous ulcers (mouth ulcers), peptic ulcers, venous ulcers, stress

ulcers, ulcerative sarcoidosis, ulcerative lichen planus, ulcerative colitis, and other systemic ulcerative conditions.^[2]

Peptic Ulcer

Peptic ulcers are the most prevalent type of ulcers and occur in the mucosal lining of the stomach or the upper portion of the small intestine. The primary causes include infection with *Helicobacter pylori*, prolonged use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), excessive gastric acid secretion, and lifestyle factors such as smoking and stress.

Ulcer Types

Fig 01 Type of ulcer.

The two most frequent causes of stomach ulcers are gastric prostaglandin loss brought on by non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and *H. pylori* bacterium infection. Hypergastrinemia (Zollinger-Ellison syndrome), viral infections like Cytomegalovirus CMV, chemotherapy, radiation, gastric outlet blockage, gastric infiltrative illnesses like malignancy, smoking, and Crohn's disease are some of the less frequent etiologies. All of these etiologies share the trait of encouraging a breach in the mucosal barrier, which exposes the gastric mucosa to the harmful effects of acid.^[3]

Peptic ulcers are classified into

- Gastric ulcers (located in the stomach)
- Duodenal ulcers (located in the duodenum)

These ulcers develop due to inflammation and erosion of the mucosal lining by gastric acid and pepsin. Pepsin, a proteolytic enzyme responsible for protein digestion, contributes significantly to mucosal damage. The treatment of peptic ulcer disease has evolved

significantly over time. The introduction of H₂ -receptor antagonists such as cimetidine and ranitidine marked a major advancement by inhibiting gastric acid secretion. Subsequently, proton pump inhibitors such as omeprazole provided more effective and sustained acid suppression, greatly improving treatment outcomes.^[4]

Fig.02: Pathogenesis of Peptic Ulcer Disease.

Pathogenesis of Peptic Ulcer Disease

Peptic ulcer disease is a multifactorial disorder caused by disruption of the gastric or duodenal mucosal integrity due to an imbalance between aggressive and protective factors.

Mechanism of Gastric Acid Secretion

Gastric acid secretion is regulated by parietal cells present in the gastric mucosa. The final step involves the H⁺/K⁺-ATPase enzyme (proton pump), which actively transports hydrogen ions into the gastric lumen using ATP.

Acid secretion is stimulated by

- Histamine (via H₂ receptors)
- Acetylcholine (via M₃ receptors)
- Gastrin (via CCK₂ receptors)

Excessive stimulation leads to increased acid production, resulting in mucosal damage. Proton pump inhibitors act by irreversibly inhibiting this enzyme.^[5]

Epidermilogy

Around 1990, approximately 10% of the American population reported experiencing peptic ulcer disease (PUD), with more than 500,000 new cases diagnosed annually in the United States. Despite this, global trends indicate a decline in both mortality rates and hospitalizations associated with PUD. This improvement is largely attributed to advances in treatment, improved hygiene, and a reduction in infections caused by *Helicobacter pylori*, which is a major underlying cause of the disease.^[6]

Additionally, the increased use of acid-suppressing medications, both prescription and over-the-counter, along with more cautious use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), has contributed to this decline. The lifetime prevalence of PUD, including gastric ulcers, is estimated to be around 5-10%, although this figure may be underestimated due to the presence of asymptomatic cases. Evidence suggests that the risk of developing gastric ulcers increases with advancing age and frequent NSAID use. Furthermore, smoking has been shown to significantly elevate the risk, approximately doubling the likelihood of ulcer development. times compared to non-smokers. The prevalence of stomach ulcers is the same for both men and women. In the United States of America's population, the frequency of *H. pylori* infection at age 60 is close to 50%. According to estimates, 25% of long-term NSAID users will get stomach ulcers.^[6]

Epidemiological evidence indicates that the prevalence of peptic ulcer (PU) disease closely mirrors the occurrence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection. The risk of ulcer development further increases with the use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), acetylsalicylic acid (ASA), and advancing age. Historically, peptic ulcer disease (PUD) contributed significantly to morbidity and mortality; however, a marked decline in its incidence was observed toward the end of the 20th century.

This reduction has been largely attributed to improvements in environmental and socioeconomic conditions, including modernization, better hygiene, and enhanced overall health standards. These changes likely reduced early-life exposure to *Helicobacter pylori*, thereby limiting its transmission. Additionally, the introduction of effective acid-suppressing therapies and targeted treatments for *Helicobacter pylori* infection played a crucial role in lowering disease prevalence.^[7]

Despite this progress, changing patterns in ulcer etiology have been observed. Increased use of NSAIDs has contributed to a decline in duodenal ulcers, which are commonly associated with *Helicobacter pylori*, while simultaneously leading to a rise in gastric ulcers linked to drug-induced mucosal injury.

Peptic ulcers remain a global health concern, particularly in developing regions where *Helicobacter pylori* infection is highly prevalent. In these areas, infection often occurs during childhood, with a large proportion of individuals affected before the age of 10 and prevalence rates exceeding 80% by middle age. In contrast, infection rates are lower in developed countries during early life but increase gradually with age.

Overall, the lifetime risk of developing a peptic ulcer is estimated to be around 10%. However, only a small proportion of individuals infected with *Helicobacter pylori* actually develop ulcers, while many experience milder gastrointestinal symptoms such as gastritis, abdominal discomfort, or non-specific dyspepsia.^[8]

Etiology

The two most common causes of gastric ulcers are the loss of protective prostaglandins due to Nonsteroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs use and infection with *Helicobacter pylori*. NSAIDs reduce prostaglandin synthesis, weakening mucosal defenses and increasing vulnerability to acid injury. In addition to these major causes, several less common factors contribute to ulcer formation, including Zollinger-Ellison syndrome, which leads to excessive gastric acid secretion. Viral infections such as Cytomegalovirus infection may also damage the gastric lining, particularly in immunocompromised individuals. Other contributing conditions include chemotherapy, radiation therapy, gastric outlet obstruction, and infiltrative diseases like gastric malignancy. Lifestyle factors such as smoking and inflammatory disorders like Crohn's disease further increase the risk. Despite their varied origins, all these etiologies share a common mechanism: disruption of the gastric mucosal barrier, allowing acid and pepsin to injure the underlying tissue and promote ulcer formation.^[9]

Path-Physiology

The injury determines the pathophysiology of stomach ulcer formation. A thorough explanation will concentrate on each since NSAID use and/or *H. pylori* infection cause 80 to 90% of stomach ulcers, respectively. First, focusing on *H. pylori*, which colonize 45-50% of the stomach mucosa globally. People get immunized against this bacterium at a young age,

particularly in developing nations with lower socioeconomic levels and crowded households. In the host, these bacteria cause an inflammatory reaction that results in an epithelial reaction, degeneration, and damage, which is known as gastritis. Patients who have this illness typically develop pan-gastritis. Due to the damage to the antral somatostatin release, increased gastrin secretion and thus higher acid generation result. Patients with the germs still present in the antrum eventually develop stomach ulcers. The more proximal stomach body's parietal cells still have full production capacity, preventing the creation of ulcers there. Not all individuals with this infection experience symptom which depends on the virulence of the bacteria and other host risk factors. The development of *cagA*, which causes greater cytokine cell death and mucosal injury, is a typical bacterial virulence factor. The second most frequent cause generating stomach ulcers is NSAID medicines. When compared to persons who do not take these medications, patients who do have a relative risk of four for stomach ulcers. NSAIDs can cause ulceration through a variety of different methods. When exposed to gastric acid, the medications themselves are weak acids. They persist in the epithelial cells and increase cellular permeability, which causes actual damage to the cells.

The reduction in prostaglandin synthesis is the main cause of NSAID-induced ulceration. NSAIDs prevent the cyclooxygenase-1 enzyme from increasing prostaglandin synthesis, which in turn promotes the secretion of gastric bicarbonate, the formation of mucus barriers, an increase in mucosal blood flow, and an expedited rate of epithelial cell restitution and repair following damage or cell death. Overall, the decrease in gastric blood flow and the mild ischemia it generates in the stomach mucosa are what cause the most detrimental physiological damage. The pathophysiology of gastric ulcer development mostly varies on the etiology, but they all result in the destruction or loss of the integrity of the stomach mucosa.^[10]

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) contribute to ulcer formation primarily by inhibiting prostaglandin synthesis, which leads to a reduction in bicarbonate and mucus secretion. As a result, the gastric mucosa becomes more vulnerable to damage from gastric acid.

Under normal conditions, several protective mechanisms help preserve the integrity of the gastric lining. These include the secretion of mucus and bicarbonate, adequate mucosal blood flow, and the action of prostaglandins, all of which work together to neutralize acid and promote tissue repair. However, disturbances in this balance such as infection with

Helicobacter pylori or prolonged NSAID use compromise these defenses. This weakening of protective factors ultimately results in cellular injury, inflammation, and the development of ulcers.^[8]

Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) refers to damage of the mucosal lining in the stomach or duodenum caused by an imbalance between aggressive factors and protective mechanisms. The aggressive factors include gastric acid, pepsin, *Helicobacter pylori*, and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), while the body's defenses consist of mucus secretion, bicarbonate production, prostaglandins, and adequate mucosal blood flow.

A major contributor to ulcer formation is the excessive secretion of gastric acid, which can erode the protective mucus barrier of the stomach. In addition, pepsin further damages the mucosa by digesting proteins, thereby overwhelming the defensive mechanisms. *Helicobacter pylori* plays a critical role in the development of ulcers by stimulating increased acid production, inducing inflammation, and weakening the integrity of the protective mucus layer.^[10]

Mechanism of Action

Helicobacter pylori is a Gram-negative bacterium uniquely adapted to survive in the highly acidic environment of the stomach. It exists in two morphological forms: a spiral form and a coccoid form, each serving specific roles. The spiral shape enhances motility and facilitates penetration into the gastric mucosa, whereas the coccoid form is associated with persistence and colonization within the mucus layer of the gastric epithelium.

By disrupting the protective mucous barrier of the stomach and duodenum, *Helicobacter pylori* exposes the underlying tissues to corrosive gastric acid, leading to mucosal injury and ulcer formation. The development of ulcers is driven by both bacterial invasion and acid-mediated damage. Key virulence factors, such as urease and flagella, enable the bacterium to survive acidic conditions, move through the mucus layer, and establish infection. Additionally, the bacterium stimulates the release of inflammatory mediators, which weaken the gastric lining and promote increased acid secretion, thereby accelerating ulcer development.^[11]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection, identification and authentication of plant material

The plant material used in the present study was collected from the Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar region, Maharashtra, India. The collected plant specimen was taxonomically identified and authenticated by a botanist from the Department of Botany, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra. The plant was identified as *Sesbania Sesban* belonging to the family *Fabaceae*. An authentication letter was issued and the voucher specimen was deposited for future reference with accession number 01399. The authentication was carried out by Dr. Arvind S. Dhabe, Sr. Professor and Head, Department of Botany, confirming that the plant is commonly found in the Marathwada region.

Processing of Crude Drugs

The collected fresh Leaf of *sesbania sesban* were subjected to shade drying and further crushed to powder, and then the powder is passed through the mesh No. 14, stored in air tight container and subjected to extraction by using Soxhlet extraction method.

Pharmacognostic Evaluation of Plant Material

Pharmacognostic evaluation was carried out to establish the identity, quality, and purity of *Sesbania Sesban Leaf*. Morphological and physicochemical parameters were determined according to standard procedures described in pharmacopoeial guidelines.^[12]

Preparation of Extracts

The extraction process was carried out using the Soxhlet extraction technique, which is widely employed for the exhaustive extraction of phytoconstituents from medicinal plants. Based on the polarity of chemical constituents and literature reports, petroleum ether, ethanol, and Ethyl acetate were selected as extraction solvents.^[13] Three different extracts of *Sesbania sesban Leaf* were prepared using petroleum ether, ethanol, and Ethyl acetate. The extraction process was continued until a colourless solvent appeared in the siphon tube, indicating complete extraction. The extracts were concentrated, dried, weighed, and stored in airtight containers for further analysis.^[14]

The percentage yield of extract was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Percentage Yield (\%)} = (\text{Weight of Extract} / \text{Weight of Powdered Drug}) \times 100$$

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Preliminary phytochemical screening was performed on petroleum ether, ethanolic, and Ethyl acetate extracts to identify the presence of various secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, saponins, terpenoids, phenolic compounds, carbohydrates, and proteins. Qualitative phytochemical analysis provides important information regarding the chemical composition of plant extracts and supports the pharmacological evaluation of medicinal plants.^[15,16]

Total Phenolic Content

The total phenolic content of *Sesbania sesban leaf* extracts was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu colorimetric method. Briefly, 0.5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was added to the extract, followed by 2 ml of 20% sodium bicarbonate solution. The reaction mixture was incubated for 60 min at room temperature, and absorbance was measured at 637 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Gallic acid was used as the standard, and results were expressed as Gallic Acid Equivalents (GAE).^[17,18]

Total Flavonoid Content

Total flavonoid content was estimated using the aluminium chloride colorimetric assay. One milliliter of extract was mixed with sodium nitrite, aluminium chloride, and sodium hydroxide solutions. The absorbance was recorded at 510 nm, and flavonoid content was expressed as Rutin Equivalents (RE) using a rutin calibration curve.^[19,20]

DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

The antioxidant activity of *Sesbania sesban leaf* extracts was evaluated by the DPPH free radical scavenging method. Different concentrations of the extract were mixed with DPPH solution and incubated for 30 min in the dark. The decrease in absorbance was measured at 517 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The percentage inhibition of DPPH radicals was calculated to determine antioxidant activity.^[21,22]

Animal Activity

IAEC Approval

Wistar rats of either sex weighing between 180-230 g were used in the present study. The experimental animals were maintained under standard laboratory conditions in the animal house of Systemic Life Sciences & Research Pvt. Ltd., Telangana, approved by the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals

(CPCSEA). Animals were housed under standard environmental conditions with 12 h light/dark cycle, temperature ($22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) and relative humidity $55 \pm 5\%$, and were provided with standard pellet diet and water ad libitum. All animals were acclimatized to the laboratory conditions for at least one week before the commencement of the experiment. The experimental protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC). The study titled “*Phytochemical and pharmacology Evaluation of Sesbania sesban Leaves Extract for Anti-ulcer Activity in Rats*” was approved with IAEC approval number **16/IAEC-II/SLSRPL/2025**. All experimental procedures were carried out in accordance with CPCSEA guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals.

Grouping

- Group I : Animals were receive 0.5 % of DMSO/ Saline water orally.
- Group II : Positive Control Ethanol(1ml/200g) oral
- Group III : Animals were receive standard drug (Ranitidine 20mg/kg)
- Group IV : Animals were receive 100mg/kg dose of Ethyl acetate extract of *Sesbania sesban* leaves (SSEAE 100mg/kg oral).
- Group V : Animal were receive 200 mg/kg dose of Ethyl acetate extract of *Sesbania sesban* leaves (SSEAE 200mg/kg oral).
- Group VI : Animals were receive 100mg/kg dose of Ethanolic extract of *Sesbania sesban* leaves (SSEE 100mg/kg oral)
- Group VII: Animals were receive 200mg/kg dose of Ethanolic extract of *Sesbania sesban* leaves (SSEE 200mg/kg oral)

Ethanol-induced model^[23]

Procedure: Male Wistar rats weighing 180-230 g were used for the study. The animals were fasted for 48 hours prior to the experiment, with free access to water. During the fasting period, they were housed in restraining cages to prevent coprophagy.

The animals were divided into different groups and administered either the appropriate vehicle (control) or a cytoprotective drug (e.g., proteinoid) via the intra-arterial route for 30 minutes prior to ulcer induction. Ulceration was induced by administering 1 mL of absolute ethanol. Untreated animals served as control.

One hour after ethanol administration, the animals were euthanized using CO₂. The stomachs were immediately excised, opened along the greater curvature, and gently rinsed under running tap water to remove gastric contents.

A circular, full-thickness section (approximately 13 mm in diameter) was obtained using a cork borer from each lobe of the fundus, just below the ridge separating the glandular and non-glandular regions of the stomach. The stomach tissues were then stretched and mounted on a foam board with the mucosal side facing upward.

Gastric mucosal damage was assessed using a subjective scoring system, where lesions were graded from 0 (no damage) to 3 (severe damage), based on the extent of visible injury.

For uniform analysis, a Plexiglas template (19 × 14 × 0.3 cm), containing four rows of six holes (each 13 mm in diameter), was used. The template was polished on one side with emery cloth and fixed onto a clear glass sheet using photographic tape along its edges.

Excised tissue samples from each stomach were carefully placed into the holes of the template. Tissue samples were analyzed in pairs to minimize sampling error. The template is positioned on a rectangular central opening of an Aristo Model T-16 cold cathode transilluminator (38 × 38 cm) containing a W-45 blue-white lamp.

A camera is mounted on a copy stand directly above the template. Photographs were taken, the film was processed in a standard manner, and a contact sheet was made from the negatives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pharmacognostic Evaluation of Plant Material

Table 1: Macroscopic Characteristics of *Sesbania sesban* Leaf.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Observation
1	Colour	Green to dark green
2	Odour	Characteristic
3	Taste	Slightly bitter
4	Shape	Oblong to lanceolate leaflets
5	Surface	Smooth

Physicochemical evaluation

Table 2: Physicochemical Standardization Parameters of *Sesbania sesban* Leaf.

Sr. No.	Standardization Parameters	Results(% w/w)
1	Ash value	4.5 %
2	Acid insoluble ash	1.5 %
3	Water soluble ash	8 %
4	Loss on Drying (LOD)	5 %

Extractive Value/ Preparation of Extracts

Table 3: Extractive Values of *Sesbania sesban* Leaf in Different Solvents Preliminary Phytochemical Screening.

Sr. No.	Solvent	Wt. of Empty Petri Dish (g)	Wt. of Petri Dish with Extract (g)	Wt. of Extract (g)	% Extractive Value (%)
1	Petroleum ether	91.95	92.08	0.13	6.5
2	Chloroform	92.46	92.60	0.14	7
3	Ethyl acetate	101.40	101.92	0.52	26
4	Acetone	91.25	91.55	0.30	15
5	Methanol	83.86	84.46	0.60	30
6	Ethanol	91.30	91.66	0.36	18
7	Water	91.53	91.71	0.18	9

Table 4: Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of Different Extracts.

(+) = Presence of phytoconstituent

(-) = Absence of phytoconstituent

Sr. No.	Phytochemical Test	Pet. Ether	Ethyl Acetate	Ethanol
1	Test for Alkaloids			
a	Dragendorff's test	-	+	+
b	Mayer's test	+	-	+
c	Wagner's test	-	+	+
d	Hager's test	-	-	-
2	Test for Flavonoids			
a	Shinoda test	-	+	+
b	Sulphuric acid test	-	+	+
c	Lead acetate test	+	+	+
3	Test for Glycosides			
a	Keller-Killiani test	+	+	+
b	Legal test	-	+	-
c	Foam test	-	+	+
4	Test for Steroids			
a	Salkowski test	+	+	+
b	Liebermann-Burchard test	-	-	+
5	Test for Proteins			

a	Biuret test	+	+	+
b	Millon's test	-	-	-
6	Test for Carbohydrates			
a	Molisch test	+	+	+
b	Fehling's test	+	-	+
c	Benedict's test	+	+	+
d	Barfoed's test	+	+	+
7	Test for Tannins & Phenolic Compounds			
a	Lead acetate test	+	+	+
b	Dil. HNO ₃ test	-	+	+
c	Dil. iodine solution	-	+	+

Total Phenolic Content

Table 5: Total phenolic Extract.

Values represent mean \pm SEM (n=3)

Sr. No.	Extract	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (Mean \pm SEM)	TPC (%) (Mean \pm SEM)
1	Ethyl acetate	100	0.536 \pm 0.0042	22.4 \pm 0.52
2	Ethanol	100	0.815 \pm 0.0051	32.8 \pm 0.64

Total flavonoid content

Table 6: Total flavonoid content.

Sr no	Extract	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	TFC %
1	Ethyl acetate Extract	50	0.078 \pm 0.0046	23.8 \pm 50
2	Ethanol Extract	50	0.094 \pm 0.0017	36.5 \pm 03

Values represent mean \pm SEM (n=3)

DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

Table 7: Antioxidant Activity.

Values represent mean \pm SEM (n=3)

Conc ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Rutin (% inhibition)	Gallic acid (%inhibition)	Ascorbic acid (%inhibition)	Ethyl acetate (%inhibition)	Ethanol Extract (% inhibition)
25	88.42 \pm 0.38	79.25 \pm 0.46	84.16 \pm 0.41	78.54 \pm 0.33	84.72 \pm 0.29
50	91.63 \pm 0.34	81.87 \pm 0.39	85.74 \pm 0.36	83.26 \pm 0.41	86.35 \pm 0.27
75	93.58 \pm 0.29	84.73 \pm 0.31	87.92 \pm 0.33	86.48 \pm 0.36	88.21 \pm 0.30
100	95.72 \pm 0.26	88.94 \pm 0.28	89.87 \pm 0.27	89.63 \pm 0.29	90.74 \pm 0.34
125	97.18 \pm 0.21	93.16 \pm 0.24	92.63 \pm 0.25	91.85 \pm 0.27	92.68 \pm 0.26

Table 08: Experimental grouping of animals for evaluation of anti-ulcer activity of *Sesbania sesban* leaf extracts.

Group	0 hr	1 hr	2 hr	3 hr	4 hr
Normal Control	37.1±0.12	37.0 ± 0.10	37.1 ± 0.11	37.0 ± 0.09	37.1 ± 0.10
Negative Control	39.5±0.18	39.6 ± 0.17	39.7 ± 0.16	39.6 ± 0.15	39.5 ± 0.14
Standard (Paracetamol150mg/kg)	39.4±0.16	38.5±0.14**	37.8±0.12**	37.3±0.11**	37.1±0.10**
ASME 100 mg/kg	39.5±0.17	39.0 ± 0.15*	38.5 ± 0.14*	38.0± 0.13**	37.8± 0.12**
ASME 200 mg/kg	39.4±0.16	38.8 ± 0.14*	38.1 ± 0.13**	37.6 ± 0.12**	37.3± 0.11**
A SEE 100 mg/kg	39.5±0.15	38.9 ± 0.14*	38.3 ± 0.13*	37.8 ± 0.12**	37.5± 0.11**
A SEE 200 mg/kg	39.4±0.14	38.6±0.13**	37.9± 0.12**	37.4± 0.11**	37.2± 0.10**

Table 09: Effect of *Sesbania sesban* Leaf Extracts in Ethanol-Induced Gastric Ulcer.

Group	Ulcer Index	Ulcer Protection (%)
Positive Control	33.18 ± 0.72	0
Negative Control	35.46 ± 0.81	-6.87
Standard (Ranitidine 20 mg/kg)	6.82 ± 0.48	79.44**
SSEAE 100	11.26 ± 0.64	62.07**
SSEAE 200	8.94 ± 0.42	73.06**
SSEE 100	13.78 ± 0.92	58.47**
SSEE 200	9.86 ± 0.76	70.29**

Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD) for six animals in each group ($n = 6$). Statistical analysis was performed by comparing treated groups with the negative control group. A value of $*p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant, while $**p < 0.01$ was considered highly significant.

Graph 1: Ulcer Index.

Graph 2: Ulcer Protection.

The anti-ulcer activity of *Sesbania sesban* (L.) Merr. leaf extracts was evaluated using ethanol-induced gastric ulcer model in experimental animals. The positive control group showed a high ulcer index of 33.18 ± 0.72 . The negative control group exhibited a slightly increased ulcer index of 35.46 ± 0.81 with no protection, indicating severe gastric mucosal damage. Pre-treatment with standard drug ranitidine (20 mg/kg) significantly reduced the ulcer index to 6.82 ± 0.48 , showing 79.44% ulcer protection. The ethyl acetate extract of *Sesbania sesban* leaves (SSEAE) at 100 mg/kg showed a reduction in ulcer index to 11.26 ± 0.64 with 62.07% protection, while SSEAE at 200 mg/kg further decreased the ulcer index to 8.94 ± 0.42 with 73.06% protection. Similarly, the ethanolic extract (SSEE) at 100 mg/kg showed an ulcer index of 13.78 ± 0.92 with 58.47% protection. The higher dose of SSEE (200 mg/kg) produced a greater reduction in ulcer index to 9.86 ± 0.76 with 70.29% ulcer protection. The results indicate that both ethyl acetate and ethanolic extracts of *Sesbania sesban* leaves significantly reduced ethanol-induced gastric ulcers in a dose-dependent manner. The ethyl acetate extract at 200 mg/kg showed better gastroprotective activity compared to the ethanolic extract and produced effects comparable to the standard drug ranitidine. These findings suggest that *Sesbania sesban* leaves possess significant anti-ulcer activity, which may be attributed to the presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and other bioactive constituents.

Table 10: Effect of *Sesbania sesban* Leaf Extracts on Gastric pH and Total Acidity.

Group	pH	Total Acidity (mEq/L)
Positive control	2.48 ± 0.20	95.36 ± 0.38
Negative control	2.05 ± 0.17	131.42 ± 0.46
Standard (Ranitidine 20 mg/kg)	6.14 ± 0.08	$24.18 \pm 0.26^{**}$
SSEAE 100	4.18 ± 0.11	$46.63 \pm 0.34^{**}$

SSEAE 200	5.36 ± 0.13	29.12 ± 0.29**
SSEE 100	4.52 ± 0.16	41.84 ± 0.37**
SSEE 200	5.22 ± 0.18	33.05 ± 0.31**

Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD) for six animals in each group (n = 6). Statistical analysis was performed by comparing treated groups with the negative control group. A value of **p* < 0.05 was considered statistically significant, while ***p* < 0.01 was considered highly significant.

Graph 3: pH

Graph 4: Total Acidity.

The effect of *Sesbania sesban* (L.) Merr. leaf extracts on gastric pH and total acidity was evaluated in ethanol-induced ulcer model. The positive control group showed low gastric pH (2.48 ± 0.20) and high total acidity (95.36 ± 0.38 mEq/L). The negative control group exhibited further decrease in pH (2.05 ± 0.17) with marked increase in total acidity (131.42 ± 0.46 mEq/L), indicating severe gastric acid secretion and mucosal damage. Treatment with standard drug ranitidine (20 mg/kg) significantly increased the gastric pH to 6.14 ± 0.08 and reduced total acidity to 24.18 ± 0.26 mEq/L. The ethyl acetate extract of *Sesbania sesban* leaves (SSEAE) at 100 mg/kg increased pH to 4.18 ± 0.11 and decreased total acidity to

46.63 ± 0.34 mEq/L. The higher dose of SSEAE (200 mg/kg) further increased pH to 5.36 ± 0.13 and reduced total acidity to 29.12 ± 0.29 mEq/L. Similarly, ethanolic extract (SSEE) at 100 mg/kg showed pH of 4.52 ± 0.16 with total acidity of 41.84 ± 0.37 mEq/L. The higher dose of SSEE (200 mg/kg) increased pH to 5.22 ± 0.18 and decreased total acidity to 33.05 ± 0.31 mEq/L. The results indicate that both extracts significantly increased gastric pH and decreased total acidity in a dose-dependent manner. The ethyl acetate extract at 200 mg/kg showed better anti-secretory effect compared to ethanolic extract and produced results comparable to standard ranitidine, suggesting significant anti-ulcer activity of *Sesbania sesban* leaves.

Ethanol-induced gastric ulcer: Gross morphological evaluation of the protective effect of *Sesbania sesban* leaf extracts on gastric mucosa

Fig.3 Ethanol-induced gastric ulcer.

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrated that *Sesbania sesban* leaves possess significant antioxidant and anti-ulcer activities. Pharmacognostic and physicochemical evaluations confirmed the authenticity and quality of the plant material. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of flavonoids, phenolics, alkaloids, glycosides, and steroids. Quantitative analysis showed higher phenolic and flavonoid contents in the ethanol extract. Both extracts exhibited strong DPPH free radical scavenging activity, indicating potent antioxidant potential. Acute toxicity studies confirmed the safety of the extracts up to 2000 mg/kg. In the ethanol-induced ulcer model, both extracts significantly reduced ulcer index and gastric acidity while increasing gastric pH. The ethyl acetate extract showed slightly better gastroprotective activity than the ethanol extract. The anti-ulcer effect may be attributed to antioxidant activity, anti-secretory action, and enhancement of mucosal defense mechanisms. Overall, the findings support the traditional use of *Sesbania sesban* as a safe and effective natural anti-ulcer agent.

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REFERENCES

1. Okabe S, Amagase K. An overview of acetic acid ulcer models--the history and state of the art of peptic ulcer research. *Biol Pharm Bul.* 1, 2005; 28(8): 1321-41. <https://doi.org/10.1248/bpb.28.1321>.
2. Xie X, Ren K, Zhou Z, Dang C, Zhang H. The global, regional and national burden of peptic ulcer disease from 1990 to 2019: a population-based study. *BMC Gastroenterol*, 2022; 22(1): 58. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12876-022-02130-2>
3. Zhang Q, Huang N, Wang J, Luo H, He H, Ding M, Deng WQ, Zou K. The H⁺/K⁺-ATPase inhibitory activities of Trametenolic acid B from *Trametes lactinea* (Berk.) Pat, and its effects on gastric cancer cells. *Fitoterapia*, 2013; 89: 210-7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fitote.2013.05.021>.

4. Wang S, Zhang T, Li D, Cao X. The global, regional and national burden of peptic ulcer disease attributable to smoking from 1990 to 2021: A population-based study. *Preventive Medicine Reports*, 2025; 51: 103019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2025.103019>.
5. Fang B, Yang S, Liu H, Zhang Y, Xu R, Chen G. Association between depression and subsequent peptic ulcer occurrence among older people living alone: A prospective study investigating the role of change in social engagement. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 2019; 122: 94-103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychores.2019.04.002>
6. Graham, D.Y. Changing patterns of peptic ulcer, gastroesophageal reflux disease and *Helicobacter pylori*: A unifying hypothesis. *Eur. J. Gastroen. Hepat.* 2003; 15: 571–572. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
7. Suerbaum, S.; Michetti, P. *Helicobacter pylori* infection. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 2002; 347: 1175–1186. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
8. Bauer, B.; Meyer, T.F. The human gastric pathogen *Helicobacter pylori* and its association with gastric cancer and ulcer disease. *Ulcers* 2011; 2011. [CrossRef]
9. Saswat Swarup Badapanda, Amanjot Kaur, Divya Jain, Deepika Bhatia Epidemiology, Pathogenesis, and Induction of Peptic Ulcer: A Comprehensive Review. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0102506882348139241210080210>
10. Ameen AA, El-Masry HG, Bashatly MYMHE. The effect of licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) on peptic ulcer in rats. *International Journal of Health Sciences*, 2022; 6(S4): 12173-83. <https://doi.org/10.53730/ijhs.v6nS4.11829>International
11. Soll AH, Jaiswal F, Rai AK, Wal P, Wal A, Singh SP. Peptic ulcer: a review on etiology, pathogenesis and treatment. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research*, 2021; 10(4): 1. <https://dx.doi.org/10.38164/AJPER/9.4.2021.01-17>
12. Dinarello CA, Cannon JG, Mancilla J et al. Interleukin-6 as an endogenous pyrogen: induction of prostaglandin E₂ in brain but not in peripheral blood mononuclear cells. *Brain Res* 1991; 562: 199–206.
13. Zheng H, Fletcher D, Kozak W et al. Resistance to fever induction and impaired acute-phase response in interleukin-1 β deficient mice. *Immunity* 1995; 3: 9–19.
14. Shimizu H, Miyoshi M, Matsumoto K et al. The effect of central injection of angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor and the angiotensin type 1 receptor antagonist on the induction by lipopolysaccharide of fever and brain interleukin-1 β response in rats. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther* 2004; 308: 865–873.

15. Dinarello CA, Cannon JG, Wolff SM et al. Tumor necrosis factor (cachectin) is an endogenous pyrogen and induces production of interleukin 1. *J Exp Med.*, 1986; 163: 1433–1450.
16. Gabay C, Kushner I. Acute-phase proteins and other systemic responses to inflammation. *N Engl J Med.*, 1999; 340: 448-454.
17. Tilg H, Trehu E, Atkins MB et al. Interleukin-6 (IL-6) as an antiinflammatory cytokine: induction of circulating IL-1 receptor antagonist and soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor p55. *Blood* 1994; 83: 113–118.
18. Obermeyer Z, Samra JK, Mullainathan S: Individual differences in normal body temperature: longitudinal big data analysis of patient records. *BMJ.* 2017; 359: j5468. 10.1136/bmj.j5468.
19. Stitt JT. Differential sensitivity in the sites of fever production by prostaglandin E1 within the hypothalamus of the rat. *Journal of Physiology.* 1991; 432: 99–110. PMID: 1886074. <https://doi.org/10.1113/jphysiol.1991.sp018378>.
20. Morimoto A, Murakami N, Sakata Y, Watanabe T, Yamaguchi K. Functional and structural differences in febrile mechanism between rabbits and rats. *Journal of Physiology.* 1990; 427: 227–239.
21. Saleh-E-In MM, Sultana N, Hossain MN, Hasan S, Islam MR. Pharmacological effects of the phytochemicals of *Anethum sowa* L. root extracts. *BMC Complement Altern Med.* 2016 Nov 14; 16(1): 464. doi: 10.1186/s12906-016-1438-9. PMID: 27842527; PMCID: PMC5396551.
22. Al-Mansur MA, Ali Siddiqi MM, Saha K. Four bioactive compounds isolated from the stem of *Anethum sowa* L. and their bioactivities. *Plant Sci. Today* [Internet]. 2023 May 19 [cited 2026 Apr. 15]; 10(2): 439-46. Available from: <https://horizonpublishing.com/journals/index.php/PST/article/view/2201>
23. Rajesh B, Jadhav & S, Khandare & G, Korde & S, Lasgare & R, Devshette & D, Palimkar & N.B, Ghiware. (2024). Pharmacological Investigation of *Manilkara zapota* Seeds Extract for the Anti-ulcer Activity on Rats. *International Journal of Zoological Investigations.* 10. 829-835. 10.33745/ijzi.2024.v10i02.080.